

Characteristics of Marianna compared with standard Krasnodarsky 424.

Indicator	Krasnodarsky 424	Marianna
Stem height (cm)	116.0	120.0
Preflag length (cm)	36.9	43.2
Preflag width (mm)	1.2	1.4
Central panicle length (cm)	19.8	21.0
Seeds (no.) in central panicle	104.4	131.7
1000-seed wt (8)	31.0	32.5
Av yield from a panicle (8)	2.1	2.4
Stem thickness (mm)	0.9	1.5
Yield (t/ha)	5.4	6.1

comparable to that of standard Krasnodarsky 424 (see table). It has tall, thick, nonlodging stems, and wide, erect, intensively pigmented leaves. Increased dynamics characterizes initial growth and development phases.

The egg-shaped grain is suitable for mechanized polishing and is highly resistant to breakage. □

Zhe 733, a high-yielding, blast (B1)-resistant, good quality indica rice for China

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In recent years, indica rice breeders have been incorporating multiple resistance into high-yielding varieties. We identified Zhe 733 as having good yield potential and B1 resistance rated 3 by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). Zhe 733 was a multiple cross of IR30, IR29, Fongxuan 4, and Chi-Kuai-Ai-Xuan, released in Mar 1991 as an early rice in the double-cropped Yangtze River area.

Zhe 733 had high, stable yield potential under normal fertilization. In regional trials in 1990, it yielded 6.4-7.8 t/ha (Table 1), 6-12% higher than the check Guangluai 4. Average growth duration was 112 d in Zhejiang, 2 d earlier than Guangluai 4. Approximately 55,000 ha is now planted to Zhe 733 in South China. Morphoagronomic characters are given in Table 2.

Table 1. B1 resistance and yield potentials of Zhe 733 in China, 1990.

Site	Yield (t/ha)		Resistance to B1 ^a	
	Zhe 733	Guangluai 4	Zhe 733	Guangluai 4
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	7.8	6.9	3	7
Changsha, Hunan	7.8	6.8	3	9
Nanchang, Jiangxi	6.5	5.5	1	
Fuzhou, Fujian	6.4	6.1	3	9

^aBy SES.

Table 2. Morphoagronomic characteristics of Zhe 733 at different sites in China, 1990.

Site	Growth duration (4)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)	Fertile grains (no./panicle)	Sterility (%)	1,000-wt (g)
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	113	81	19.8	89	72	19.1	25.8
Changsha, Hunan	111	83	20.4	98	80	18.4	26.9
Nanchang, Jiangxi	112	79	19.0	84	67	20.2	25.7
Fuzhou, Fujian	111	80	19.1	90	73	18.9	25.7

Appearance, milling recovery, chemical properties, cooking and eating quality meet the China national index for high quality rice. Grain length is 6.8 mm, with a 2.8 length-breadth ratio. The grain is semitranslucent with 24.9% amylose,

10.3% protein content, low-gelatinization temperature (5.3 alkali spreading value), and medium gel consistency (60 mm). Hulling recovery is 81.9%; milling recovery, 74.1%; and head rice recovery, 52.6%. □

Response to nitrogen of new dwarf fragrant rice varieties for transplanted conditions

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Pusa Basmati 1 and Kasturi are new dwarf fragrant rice varieties released in India in 1990. Pusa Basmati 1, a semi-dwarf of medium duration (133-135 d), has a yield potential of 4 t/ha. Kasturi is semitall, of medium duration (130-135 d) with a yield potential over 4 t/ha. Both varieties have long, slender grains with strong aroma. Kasturi also has good kernel elongation. Both are suited to the irrigated ecosystem and have export potential.

We compared Pusa Basmati 1, Kasturi and another promising variety, HKR228, with local check Basmati 370 at 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha under optimum management. The soil was Aquic Hapludoll, silt loam, with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq/100 g, and 0.1% total N. The

Performance of newly released Basmati rice varieties at different N levels at Pantnagar, 1990 wet season.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha) at 14% moisture			
	N ₆₀	N ₉₀	N ₁₂₀	Mean
Pusa Basmati 1	2.8	3.1	3.2	3.0
Kasturi	3.0	3.5	3.7	3.4
HKR228	3.0	3.4	3.5	3.3
Basmati 370 (local check)	2.2	2.8	2.8	2.6
Mean	2.8	3.2	3.3	
<u>Treatment</u>	<u>LSD (0.05)</u>			
Variety	0.2			
N rate	0.5			
Variety × N interaction	ns			

experiment was laid out in split-plot design, with four replications (N rate in main plots, and varieties in subplots).

Seedlings were raised in wet nurseries (20 Jun sowing) and transplanted on 20 Jul with basal application of 17.6 kg P, 24.2 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha as per normal practice. We applied urea in three splits: 1/2 basal, 1/4 at tillering, and 1/4 at 1 wk before panicle initiation.

The Basmati varieties showed no differential response to N. N response